

A STUDY OF ADJUSTMENT PROBLEMS OF TRIBAL SCHOOL GOING ADOLESCENTS IN RELATION TO THEIR GENDER

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Abstract

In the modern society, life is becoming very complex and conflicting day by day. If a person is well adjusted only then one can survive without psychological stress resulting from maladjustment. Generally adolescence is believed to be a period of great stress and storm as rapid physical as well as mental changes occur during this period. In the present study an attempt has been made to understand the adjustment problems of tribal school going adolescents in relation to their gender and type of institution. The investigator selected a sample of 320 senior secondary school students studying classes 10+1 and 10+2 in different institutions in district Kinnaur of Himachal Pradesh by adopting purposive sampling method. Adjustment problems are defined as the problems experienced by an individual in four wide areas viz, Home, Health, Social and Emotional areas as assessed through the tool developed by Bell's Adjustment Inventory by Dr. R. K. Ojha. The results revealed that 1) There is no significant gender-wise difference in adjustment problems faced by tribal school going adolescents with respect to home and health adjustment. Tribal school going male and female adolescents faced more or less the same problems of adjustment in these areas. 2) Tribal schools going female adolescents have significantly higher problems of adjustment in social and emotional areas than tribal school going male adolescents. 3) There is no significant gender-wise difference in adjustment problems faced by tribal school going adolescents with respect to overall adjustment.

Keywords: *Adolescents, tribal school, Adjustment, Adjustment problems*

INTRODUCTION

Education is the process of training the individuals or the adjustment in different life situations. Main concern of the teacher is to develop the capacity among the students for adjusting in home, school and in society.

Adjustment is a built-in mechanism for coping with the problematic or other realities of life. Adjustment has been considered as an index to integration; a harmonious behavior of the individual by which other individuals of society recognize the person as well adjusted (Pathak, 1990). If the adolescent boys and girls are unhealthy, socially maladjusted, educationally backward, emotionally disturbed and cannot fit in normal situation, they become problem to themselves and to their families and community. The boys and girls can adjust better if they are properly guided by their parents, teachers or any other. Therefore, it becomes important to study their adjustment problems. Adolescence is the period of transition between childhoods to adulthood. It is a period when rapid physiological changes and demands for new social roles take place. It is a period of demanding significant adjustments to the physical and social changes and distinguishes childhood behavior from adult behavior. The stage of adolescence brings a number of physical and physiological changes. The genetic factors interact with socio-economic status, health, nutrition and emotional level to shape the pattern of growth and development during adolescence.

From the review of related literature, it is clear that most of the studies have been conducted on the adjustment problems of rural and urban students of secondary school stage in different districts of Himachal Pradesh but there is lack of research work with respect to adjustment problems of tribal students. Hence, the present investigation was undertaken by the investigator to study the adjustment problems of tribal school going male and female adolescents studying in different institutions in district Kinnaur of Himachal Pradesh. The results of the present study will be beneficial for students, parents and teachers. The study will make students aware about their own adjustment problems in various areas and also enable the parents to understand the nature of adjustment problems faced by their children and hence helping them in attaining better adjustment.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Lichter (2005) in his study found that there was no significant difference in the pre and post test scores of Indian and Thai in educational adjustment. He also found a significant difference between boys and girls in control group was reported after pre-test in Indian adolescents.

Gupta (2006) studied the adjustment problems of senior secondary school students of Himachal Pradesh and found:

- There is no significant difference in the mean score of home adjustment problems of male and female students of senior secondary school stage.
- There is no significant difference in the mean score of social adjustment problems of male and female students of senior secondary school stage.
- Health adjustment problems of male and female students do not differ significantly.
- There is no significant difference in the mean score of emotional adjustment problems of male and female students of senior secondary school stage.
- There is no significant difference in the mean score of school adjustment problems of male and female students of senior secondary school stage.

Patwardhan and Vanita (2007) in their study found that attitude towards menstruation and health adjustment were highly correlated, whereas, the correlation of attitude towards menstruation and the other four areas of adjustment- home and family, personal and emotional, social and educational were not significant. Girls from two types of school showed similar attitude towards menstruation. They also exhibited similar adjustment except in home and family adjustment. Girls from co- educational schools were excelled in home and family adjustment.

Pandey (2007) in his study concluded that male and female pass outs of JNV's were seemed to be similar in home, health and educational area of adjustment. They differed significantly in only social and emotional areas of adjustment.

Deshwal and Deshwal (2008) conducted a study on adjustment among female students in relation to extroversion, neuroticism, psychoticism. The study reported that:

- There exists no significant difference in the adjustment of high and low extrovert female students.
- Highly neurotic female students are more adjusted than low neurotic female students.
- Highly psychotic female students are more adjusted than low psychotic female students.

Akram (2010) in his study found that social adjustment depends upon the self-concept and self-concept depends upon age, gender and education level.

Zareena and Vatsala (2011) found that the socio-economic factor did not have an effect on the achievement of the students but the qualification of the father did have an effect on their achievement. There was no significant difference in the time management and capacity of the

high and low achievers. Low achievers did show more adjustment problems than the high achievers.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The following objectives have been formulated in the present study.

1. To study the distribution of adjustment problem scores of tribal school going adolescents.
2. To study the adjustment problems faced by tribal school going male adolescents.
3. To study the adjustment problems faced by tribal school going female adolescents.
4. To study the gender-wise difference in adjustment problems faced by tribal school going adolescents with respect to
 - I. Home adjustment
 - II. Health adjustment
 - III. Social adjustment
 - IV. Emotional adjustment
 - V. Overall adjustment

DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study was delimited in its scope to the following aspects:

1. The study was delimited to a sample of 320 tribal school going adolescents studying in classes 10+1 and 10+2.
2. Further, the study was delimited to tribal region Nichar and Kalpa of district Kinnaur of Himachal Pradesh.

RESEARCH METHOD USED

To achieve the objectives of the present study, Survey technique under Descriptive Method of Research' was used by the researcher.

SAMPLING

In the present study the investigator selected a sample of 320 senior secondary school students studying classes 10+1 and 10+2 in different institutions in district Kinnaur of Himachal Pradesh by adopting purposive sampling method.

RESEARCH TOOLS USED

In order to collect the requisite data, Bell's Adjustment Inventory by Dr. R. K. Ojha was used.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

In order to study the nature of distribution of adjustment problem scores of tribal school going adolescents descriptive statistics like mean, Median, mode, standard deviation,
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skewness and kurtosis were calculated. For computing the gender-wise significance of difference in adjustment problems of tribal school going adolescents, t-test was used.

1.1 DISTRIBUTION OF ADJUSTMENT PROBLEM SCORES

The distribution of adjustment problem scores of tribal school going adolescents along with mean, median, mode, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis is given in table-1.

Table-1

Frequency Distribution of Adjustment Problem Scores of Tribal School Going Adolescents (N-320)

Class Interval	Frequency	Cumulative frequency	Cumulative frequency (percentage)
90-99	05	320	100
80-89	12	315	98.43
70-79	33	303	94.68
60-69	51	270	84.37
50-59	66	215	67.18
40-49	86	153	47.81
30-39	48	67	20.93
20-29	15	19	5.93
10-19	03	04	1.25
0-9	01	01	0.31
Total	320		

Mean	Median	Mode	S.D.	Skewness	Kurtosis
52.28	50.56	47.12	16.20	+0.31	0.27

Table-1 shows that the value of mean and median of the adjustment problem scores of tribal school going adolescents as 52.28 and 50.56 respectively, which are quite proximate to each other. The value of standard deviation is 16.20. Further, the value of skewness is +0.31 which shows that the curve is positively skewed. In addition to this the value of kurtosis was calculated to be 0.27 which is indicating that the curve is platykurtic in nature.

1.2 ADJUSTMENT PROBLEMS OF TRIBAL SCHOOL GOING MALE ADOLESCENTS

Mean and standard deviation of adjustment problem scores of tribal school going male adolescents with respect to four areas of adjustment are given in table-2.

Table-2

Area-wise Mean and Standard Deviation of Adjustment Problem Scores of Tribal School going Male Adolescents

Sr. No.	Adjustment Problem Areas	Number=160	
		Mean(M)	S.D.
1.	Home	14.16	5.20
2.	Health	9.69	5.05
3.	Social	15.72	2.65
4.	Emotional	12.69	6.45

It is evident from table-2 that the calculated mean values for the adjustment problems of tribal school going male adolescents were found to be 14.16, 9.69, 15.72 and 12.69 for home, health, social and emotional areas respectively. From these values it can be interpreted that the tribal school going male adolescents have maximum problems of adjustment in social area as the mean value of this area was found to be 15.72 and next in order is home and emotional areas. In health area tribal school going male adolescents faced minimum problems of adjustment as the mean value for this area was found to be 9.69.

The hierarchy of adjustment problems of tribal school going male adolescents with respect to four areas of adjustment in descending order is diagrammatically presented in figure-1.

Figure-1

Bar Diagram Showing Adjustment problems of Tribal Male

Hence, it can be concluded that the tribal school going male s face maximum problems of adjustment in social area and adolescents of minimum problems in health area.

1.3 ADJUSTMENT PROBLEMS OF TRIBAL SCHOOL GOING FEMALE ADOLESCENTS

Mean and standard deviation of adjustment problem scores of tribal school going female adolescents with respect to four areas of adjustment are given in table-3.

Table-3

Area-wise Mean and Standard Deviation of Adjustment Problem Scores of Tribal School going Female Adolescents

Sr. No.	Adjustment Problem Areas	Number=160	
		Mean(M)	S.D.
1.	Home	13.17	4.55
2.	Health	9.40	4.50
3.	Social	16.71	4.9
4.	Emotional	14.81	6.36

It is apparent from table-4 that the calculated mean values for the adjustment problem scores of tribal school going female adolescents were found to be 13.17, 9.40, 16.71 and 14.81 for home, health, social and emotional areas respectively. From these values it can be interpreted that the tribal school going female adolescents have maximum problems of adjustment in social area as the mean value of this area was found to be 16.71 and next in order is emotional and home areas. In health aren tribal school going female adolescents faced minimum problems of adjustment.

Bar Diagram showing hierarchy of adjustment problems of tribal school going female adolescents is presented in figure-2.

Figure-2

Bar Diagram Showing Adjustment problems of Female adolescents

Hence, it can be concluded that the tribal school going adolescents face maximum problems of adjustment in social area and next in order is emotional and home areas. Tribal female adolescents female face minimum problems of adjustment in health area.

2.1 GENDER-WISE COMPARISON OF ADJUSTMENT PROBLEMS FACED BY TRIBAL SCHOOL GOING ADOLESCENTS

The summary of statistical calculations for finding the significance of difference in the mean scores of adjustment problems faced by tribal male and female school going adolescents given in table -4.

Table-4

Significance of Difference in the Mean Scores of Adjustment Problems faced by Male and Female Tribal School going Adolescents

Sr. No.	Variable	Male Group	Female Group	t-value
1.	Home Adjustment	N=160	N=160	1.86 ^{NS}
		M=14.16	M=13.17	
		SD= 5.20	SD=4.55	
2.	Health Adjustment	N=160	N=160	0.56 ^{NS}
		M=9.69	M=9.40	
		SD=5.05	SD=4.50	
3.	Social Adjustment	N=160	N=160	2.30*
		M=15.42	M=16.71	
		SD=2.65	SD=4.90	
4.	Emotional Adjustment	N=160	N=160	2.98**
		M=12.69	M=14.81	
		SD= 6.45	SD=6.36	
5.	Overall Adjustment	N=160	N=160	0.65 ^{NS}
		M=51.57	M=52.75	
		SD=16.50	SD=15.60	

HOME ADJUSTMENT

From table-4 (Sr. No. 1) it is clear that the calculated value of t for comparing the means of home adjustment scores of male and female tribal school going adolescents came out to be 1.86, for df-318, which is less than the table value (1.97) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the Hypothesis No.1 (1) that, "There will be significant gender-wise difference in adjustment problems faced by tribal school going adolescents with respect to home adjustment" is rejected.

HEALTH ADJUSTMENT

Table-4 (Sr. No.2 shows that the calculated value of 't' for comparing the gender-wise means of health adjustment scores of tribal school going adolescents came out to be 0.56, for df-318, which is less than the table value (1.97) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the Hypothesis

No.1 (ii) that, "There will be significant gender-wise difference in adjustment problems faced by tribal school going adolescents with respect to health adjustment" is rejected.

SOCIAL ADJUSTMENT

It is apparent from table-4 (Sr. No.3) that the calculated value of comparing the means of social adjustment scores of male and female tribal school going adolescents came out to be 2.30, for df-318, which is more than the table value (1.97) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the Hypothesis No.1 (iii) that, "There will be significant gender-wise difference in adjustment problems faced by tribal school going adolescents with respect to social adjustment" is accepted. **EMOTIONAL ADJUSTMENT**

It is evident from table-4 (Sr. No.4) that the calculated value of t for comparing the gender-wise means of emotional adjustment scores of tribal school going adolescents came out to be 2.98, for df =318, which is more than the table value (2.59) at 0.01 level of significance. Hence, the Hypothesis No.1 (iv) that, "There will be significant gender-wise difference in adjustment problems faced by tribal school going adolescents with respect to emotional adjustment" is accepted.

OVERALL ADJUSTMENT

Table-4 (Sr. No.5) depicts that the calculated value of F for comparing the means of overall adjustment scores of male and female tribal school going adolescents came out to be 0.65, for df- 318, which is less than the table value (1.97) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the Hypothesis No.1 (v) that, "There will be no significant gender-wise difference in adjustment problems faced by tribal school going adolescents with respect to overall adjustment is rejected.

Male and female tribal school going adolescents did not differ significantly in their overall adjustment. Tribal school going female adolescents have slightly higher mean score (52.75) of adjustment problems than their male counterparts (45.57), but the difference is not significant statistically.

CONCLUSIONS

- There is no significant gender-wise difference in adjustment problems faced by tribal school going adolescents with respect to home and health adjustment. Tribal school going male and female adolescents faced more or less the same problems of adjustment in these areas.
- Tribal schools going female adolescents have significantly higher problems of adjustment in social and emotional areas than tribal school going male adolescents.

- There is no significant gender-wise difference in adjustment problems faced by tribal school going adolescents with respect to overall adjustment.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

The present study has the following implications to the field of education:

1. Adjustment problems of adolescents are increasing day-by-day in the present Indian society due to modernization and westernization. It becomes essential now to develop good physical and mental health in the youth to prevent adjustment problems during adolescent period of life to the fullest possible extent.
2. The results of the present study revealed that tribal school going female adolescents faced significantly higher problems of adjustments in social and emotional areas than their male counterparts. Home as well as social environment is the important regulatory factors of adolescents' behavior. Though adjustment problem is a general problem adolescent, it becomes serious when they develop maladaptive behavior as a result of unresolved continuous stress or emotional problems.
3. Healthy childrearing practices of parents can create appropriate environment of love and discipline that is favorable for helping children in need of overcoming stress.
4. Teachers must help the students to understand the importance of making adjustment in life. Parent Teacher Associations must be maintained to share their ideas and to plan together for the better adjustment of tribal adolescents.
5. Various types of co-curricular activities should be organized frequently to promote qualities such as corporation, tolerance, open-mindedness and sharing of responsibilities to enhance their adjustment.

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